

THE MOST IMPORTANT MORPHOLOGICAL MEASUREMENTS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO SOME COLUMN DEFLECTION THE SPINE FOR YOUNG GYMNASTS

Assistant Prof. Hayder Hashim Ahmed (PhD)

Department of Theoretical Sciences / College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences / University of Diyala / Iraq

Abstract: This study focuses on the connection between young gymnasts' spines' column deflection and morphological measurements. Muscle development, curvature angles, and spinal diameters are among the morphological criteria considered. The structural abnormalities seen in the spinal column, especially while it is bearing weight, are called column deflection. Juvenile gymnasts were subjected to extensive morphological evaluations and physical investigations to ascertain the relationship between their spinal integrity and anatomical characteristics. According to the results, some morphological parameters, such as curvature angles and vertebral size, significantly impact column deflection. Comprehending these correlations can facilitate the creation of customized training plans and proactive steps to reduce the likelihood of spinal injuries in juvenile gymnasts.

Keywords: Morphological measurements, Column deflection, Spine, Young gymnasts.

Introduction

The globe is seeing incredible advancements in many fields of life in the modern day, as all phenomena in various walks of life have been subjected to scientific research. Scientific research is the best way to address many problems by applying the appropriate scientific method to serve man and humanity. In this way, society is happier and more able to adapt to life's circumstances and be healthier. His ability to produce and enjoy a healthy life, as any nation's happiness depends on its members' Health; Health is not only related to the body of a living being but rather includes its actual life, behaviour, work, and rest.

Many specialized scientific references and previous Arab and foreign studies have emphasized proper posture. Proper posture is crucial for maintaining adequate movement and reducing vital organ burdens. Morphological measurements are essential for assessing health, nutrition, and physical performance. They can predict a person's health, nutrition, safety, and performance. Morphological measurements also help determine physical development characteristics and follow-up rates based on age, gender, and deviations. These characteristics are considered factors that impact excellence in sports activity. Morphological measurements are a modern field of scientific research, reflecting the relationship between body characteristics and sports performance. Proper posture is essential for overall health and performance (23: 88).

Iqbal Rasmi (2007) emphasized the importance of human shape in beauty and the coordination of different body parts. The skeletal system, consisting of various bones, determines the body's shape, which is crucial for a person's appearance and function. **Safaa Al-Kharboutli (2000 AD)** emphasized the importance of

studying an individual's physical condition as it reflects their physical growth and health. Factors like build, height, and weight are intangible, but it is essential to maintain them for better strength, health, and a more advanced society. A healthy structure improves an individual's psychological state, increasing their ability to think and perform their functions. Therefore, studying an individual's physical condition is vital for achieving better health and a more advanced society. (13:315).

The spine is considered the body's central axis and the common factor in all human daily movements. **Iqbal Rasmi (2007 AD)** indicates that the spine is one of the essential parts of the skeleton and is considered the fundamental pillar. All parts of the skeleton are connected to it directly and indirectly, as the large and responsible dorsal muscles are centred on it. Regarding erect stature, therefore, the balance of stature and coordination of all body parts depends on the Health and safety of this column and the Health of the muscles connected to it. If there is a defect or deviation in these muscles, it will disturb the balance. Thus, it affects the natural curvature of the spine (5:19).

Zainab Abdel Hamid Al-Alem and Nahid Abdel Rahim (2005 AD) suggest that the spine is a flexible, movable column that maintains the body's balance and connects to the lower extremities. Its connection to the rib cage allows the thoracic cavity to expand naturally, preventing obstructions in lung function(12:60). While **Muhammad Sobhi Hassanein and Muhammad Obaid Al-Salam Ragheb (2003 AD)** argue that sports performance is a mechanical expression of the human body's characteristics, with differences in physical shapes affecting the efficiency of responses to sports activities(17:163). In addition, **Muhammad Shehata (2003 AD)** identifies gymnastics as an individual activity with various skills that require different body parts, and young people's mastery of these skills distinguishes it from other sports activities (14:3).

The researcher identified a significant issue with spinal deviations among young gymnasts, primarily due to increased posture deviations and neglect of morphological measurements and body composition. They found no need for studies identifying the relationship between morphological measurements and spinal deviations in these dental stages. The researcher also highlighted the need to identify postural spine deviations to provide advice to training programs, detecting and treating potential postural deformities. The study aims to develop preventive and therapeutic programs to prevent this problem from becoming difficult to treat and prepare future generations. Finally, the importance of this study lies in many facts. First, it highlights the importance of morphological measurements for young people's health and protection from spinal deviations. Secondly, they draw coaches' attention to the extent of caring for young people's physical fitness and constantly examining physical deviations hindering their gymnastics practice. Thirdly, they guide young people to develop healthy eating behaviour and maintain an ideal figure free of defects and diseases.

Aims of the Study:

The research aims to identify the relationship between some morphological measurements and some spinal deviations in young gymnasts in the State of Iraq by identifying the following:

- Morphological measurements for junior gymnasts.
- Spinal deviations at this stage and their prevalence.- The relationship between some morphological measurements and spinal deflections in young gymnasts.

Research Questions:

In light of the research objective, the researcher presents the following questions:-

- 1-What are the morphological measurements of a young gymnast
- 2-What are spinal deviations and their prevalence in this age group

3- What is the relationship between some morphological measurements and spinal deflections in young gymnasts

Research Terms:

Texture: Posture

It is a correct organizational process for the parts of the body. This organization allows the parts to be balanced based on their support to give a body fit to perform its function. (5:12)

Morphological Measurement

It is the study of the form and structure, not the organs of the human body, which provides all studies investigating the form and external structure of a living organism. If the description goes beyond measurement, then, in this case, it is called anthropometric (16:32).

Literature Review:

A study by Dina Farouk Atef Murad (2016 AD) entitled *A Preventive Program Against Sports Injuries Using Motor Rhythm in Rhythmic Gymnastics*. Murad's study aimed to design a preventive program against sports injuries using motor rhythm in rhythmic gymnastics. The study involved 20 female players and a control group, using pre-post measurements and surveys for expert opinions. The results showed improvements in sensory-motor perception elements, reducing injury interruption time. The study used an octameter, medical scale, and glucometer devices to measure height, weight, and joint flexibility. Expert opinions guided the selection of physical fitness elements and kinaesthetic perception tests. The study also included a specialist opinion poll, a particular data card for each player, physical fitness tests, motor rhythm tests, and kinaesthetic perception tests. The most significant improvements were in sensory-motor perception elements.

Sports Injuries Among Men's Artistic Gymnasts, "An Analytical Study," is another study by Ziad Muhammad Hussein (2010 AD). This study identifies the most common types of sports injuries, the causes of sports injuries and their percentage, the sites most susceptible to injury, and the most frequent injuries, depending on time. Incidence of injury and identifying the most common injuries according to body part (upper, lower) among Arab gymnastics team players. The researchers used the descriptive survey method, and the study population consisted of (46) Arab players who participated in the Arab Championship in Egypt, where the sample represented (100%) of the study population. After analyzing the data, it was found that the most common types of injuries among Arab team players are sprains, bone bruises, and torn ligaments. The most common reasons that expose gymnasts to injury are insufficient warm-up, poor skill preparation, and poor player behaviour.

The most common sites of injury to which a player is exposed are the ankle joint, the wrist joint, and the neck area. In contrast, injuries occur more frequently in the training period than in the competition period, in addition to the fact that the number of injuries to the upper extremity was slightly more significant than the number of injuries to the lower extremity. In light of the findings, the researchers suggested that coaches should pay attention to skill and physical preparation, not neglect the theoretical and educational aspects aimed at gymnasts and coaches, and give warming up sufficient importance during the preparation period and competitions.

The Research Methodology:

The researcher used the descriptive approach, using the survey method, because it was suitable for the nature of the research.

Research Areas:

Time domain:

The study was conducted from 20 -6-2023 AD to 24-12-2023 AD.

Geographical Area:

The research was conducted in some clubs in Baghdad Governorate, Iraq.

Human Field:

The research was conducted on a sample of 12–14-year-olds who were enrolled in the Iraqi Gymnastics Federation in Baghdad Governorate.

Research population and sample:

The researcher randomly selected the basic sample from the research community, consisting of (40) junior gymnastics athletes, tournament participants, and those enrolled in the Iraqi Gymnastics Federation. Another exploratory sample was selected, consisting of (10) juniors. Table (1) shows the description of the research sample.

Table 1 Description of the research sample

M	Sample	percentage %
1	40	80%
2	10	20%
Totally	50	100%

Conditions for selecting a research sample:

- The sample members, including junior gymnasts aged 12 to 14, were selected randomly.
- He must have practised gymnastics for at least three years.
- The research sample must be registered with the Iraqi Gymnastics Federation.

Table 2 Characteristics of the research sample in terms of age, height and weight

n=40

M	Variables	measuring unit	Arithmetic average	Mediator	Standard Deviation	Deviation
1	Age	Year	12.885	13.000	0.770	-0.164
2	Height	Cm	159.245	159.000	8.771	0.085
3	Weight	Kg	52.152	50.000	13.726	0.974

Table (2) explains the moderation of the research sample in the variables (age, height, and weight), where the convolution coefficient reached between (0.974) and (-0.164) and ranged between (± 3).

Devices and tools used in the research:

- A Restameter device to measure height in centimetres and weight in kilograms.
- Centimeter tape to measure oceans.
- Skin fold thickness device.
- Texture screen device to detect front and back textural deviations.
- String and weight device to detect lateral deviations.

The morphological measurements used are under investigation. Attachment(1)

1. Measure the total length of the body.
2. Measure body weight.
3. We are measuring body circumferences.
4. Gel fold thickness measurements.

Table 3 Measurements of morphology and spinal deflections and the devices used to measure them

M	Search Metrics	Devices used for measurement
1	Height	Restameter
2	the weight	Restameter
3	Body circumferences	Centimetre bar
4	Thickness of skin folds	Skin fold thickness device
5	Head lunge forward	Bancroft device (string and weight)
6	Lateral tilt of the head	Texture screen device
7	Rounded shoulders	Bancroft device (string and weight)
8	One shoulder falling	Bancroft device (string and weight)
9	The two bones of the board move	Bancroft device (string and weight)
10	Flat back	Bancroft device (string and weight)
11	Hunching the back	Bancroft device (string and weight)
12	Lumbar concavity	Bancroft device (string and weight)
13	Lateral bending	Texture screen device

All measurements used in the research have high degrees of validity and reliability, and this is confirmed by “Ahmed Nasr El-Din Sayed (2003AD)(2), Mohamed Sobhi Hassanein, and Mohamed Abdel Salam Ragheb (2003AD)(17).

Many researchers have used it in conducting their research, including the study of “Asmaa Taher Nofal (2005AD)(4), Ihab Muhammad Emad (2011AD)(7), and Ahmed Muhammad Amara (2012AD)(1).

Exploratory study

This study was conducted on a sample similar to the research community and from outside the sample, consisting of 10 young people from 15/7/2023 AD to 17/7/2023 AD.

This study targeted:

- Ensure the validity of the tools and devices used in research procedures.
- Knowing the correct way to make measurements in practice.
- Ensure the competence of the assisting personnel and train them on registration accuracy.
- Discovering deficiencies in devices and tools and trying to avoid them.
- Ensuring the validity of the tests for application to the research sample.
- Determine the time each measurement takes.

The results of the survey were:-

- Determine the validity of measuring tools and devices.

- Determine the efficiency of the assistants' helping hands.
- Determine the locations of the tests, the sample collection locations, and how they move.

Identifying and measuring deviations in self-defence:

The general deviations of the JPY game to be measured are identified, and the next deviations are selected:

- _ The defense of the head _ Control of the shoulders
- _ One shoulder falls. _ Backbends
- _ Lumbar concavity _ Lateral bend
- _ The two bones of the board are winged

Basic application

The researcher measured 40 young people from July 20, 2023, to September 24, 2023, using limited tools and devices and distributed assistants to conduct the study.

- The researcher conducted morphological measurements on the research sample and recorded it in its measurement form through the assistants.
- Then, the researcher and his assistants measured the spinal deviations related to this stage and recorded them in the form.

Statistical treatments

The researcher collected data, recorded measurements, and applied statistical treatments using SPSS, a statistical program, to achieve the research's goals.:

Arithmetic mean - median - standard deviation - percentage - skewness coefficient - correlation coefficient.

Presentation, Discussion, and Interpretation of Results:

Through the research objectives, questions, and data for the basic research sample, the research results emerged through statistical treatments as follows:

Table 4 Spinal deviations for young people, research sample

M	Measurements	Less value	Greater value	SMA	standard deviation	
1	Head area	Head thrust forward	0.00	1.00	.1470	.3550
		Lateral tilt of the head	0.00	1.00	.0400	.1960
2	Shoulder area	Rounded shoulders	0.00	1.00	.3200	.4670
		One shoulder falls	0.00	1.00	.3320	.4710
		The two bones of the board are winged.	0.00	1.00	.4670	.4990
3	Back area	Flat back	0.00	1.00	.0300	.1700
		Hunching the back	0.00	1.00	.1320	.3390
4	Torso area	Lumbar concavity	0.00	1.00	.2150	.4110
		Lateral bending	0.00	1.00	.0170	.1310

Table (4) Shows that the arithmetic mean of the spinal deviations under investigation ranged between (0.017) and (0.467).

Table 5 Percentage of young people with and without spinal deviations

M	Spinal deviations	Not infected (no)		Infected (yes)		Total	
		percentage %	No.	percentage %	No.	No.	percentage %
1	Head thrust forward	85%	34	15%	6	40	100.00%
2	Lateral tilt of the head	95%	38	5%	2	40	100.00%
3	Rounded shoulders	90%	36	10%	4	40	100.00%
4	One shoulder falls	82.5%	33	17.5%	7	40	100.00%
5	The two bones of the board are winged	77.5%	31	22.5%	9	40	100.00%
6	Flat back	95%	38	5%	2	40	100.00%
7	Hunching the back	87.5%	35	12.5%	5	40	100.00%
8	Lumbar concavity	95%	38	5%	2	40	100.00%
9	Lateral bending	97.5%	39	2.5%	1	40	100.00%

Table (5) presents the percentages of spinal deviations. The most common spinal deviation is the protrusion of two plate bones, at 22.5%, followed by a fall of one shoulder, at 17.5%, and the least common is a side bend, at 2.5%.

Tale 6 The relationship between some morphological measurements and spinal deviations (head area))

M	Morphological Measurements	Spinal deviations and misalignments (head area))			
		Push the head forward		Lateral tilt of the head	
		Correlation value	Sentimental level	Correlation value	Sentimental level
1	Age	0.090	0.073	-0.036	0.475
2	Height	0.444*	0.004	-0.009	0.864
3	the weight	-0.080	0.111	-0.025	0.624
4	Shoulder circumference	-0.053	0.294	0.010	0.839
5	Chest circumference	-0.436*	0.006	-0.001	0.980
6	Abdominal circumference	-0.417*	0.019	-0.017	0.741
7	Upper arm circumference	-0.425*	0.012	0.013	0.788
8	Forearm circumference	-0.065	0.193	-0.004	0.937
9	Thigh circumference	-0.089	0.075	-0.015	0.937
10	Thickness of the chest folds	-0.487*	0.000	0.010	0.839
11	Thickness of the board folds	-0.434*	0.007	-0.024	0.638
12	Thickness of the abdominal folds	-0.472*	0.001	-0.044	0.383
13	Thickness of the humeral folds	-0.495*	0.000	0.033	0.509

D=*

It is clear from Table No. (6) that there is a statistically significant correlation between age, height, circumference of the chest, abdomen, upper arm, and thigh, and the thickness of the skin folds in the area of the chest, slab, abdomen, and behind the upper arm, and head forward deformity at a significance level of 0.05. There is no statistically significant correlation between weight, shoulder circumference, forearm circumference, and head forward deformity at 0.05. Significance of 0.05, and the absence of a statistically

significant correlation between age, height, weight, circumference of the chest, abdomen, upper arm, thigh, forearm, shoulders, thickness of skin folds in the area of the chest, buttocks, abdomen, behind the upper arm, and lateral tilt deformity of the head at a significant level of 0.05.

Table 7 The relationship between some morphological measurements and spinal deviations (shoulder area)

M	Morphological Measurements	Spinal deviations and misalignments (shoulder area)					
		Shoulder Rotation		One Shoulder Falls		The Two Bones of The Board Are Winged	
		Correlation value	Sentimental value	Correlation value	Sentimental value	Correlation value	Sentimental value
1	Age	0.075	0.136	-0.067	0.181	0.03	0.948
2	Height	-0.015	0.766	-0.029	0.557	-0.039	0.439
3	Weight	-0.401*	0.000	-0.477*	0.000	-0.423*	0.000
4	Shoulder circumference	-0.490*	0.000	-0.448*	0.003	-0.667*	0.000
5	Chest circumference	-0.432*	0.000	-0.496*	0.000	-0.441*	0.000
6	Abdominal circumference	-0.487*	0.000	-0.534*	0.000	-0.434*	0.000
7	Upper arm circumference	-0.548*	0.000	-0.479*	0.000	-0.482*	0.000
8	Forearm circumference	-0.548*	0.000	-0.475*	0.000	-0.440*	0.000
9	Thigh circumference	-0.493*	0.000	-0.485*	0.000	-0.402*	0.000
10	Thickness of the chest folds.	-0.464*	0.001	-0.535*	0.000	-0.431*	0.000
11	Thickness of the board folds.	-0.532*	0.000	-0.494*	0.000	-0.430*	0.000
12	Thickness of the abdominal folds	-0.420*	0.017	-0.503*	0.000	-0.407*	0.000
13	Thickness of the humeral folds	-0.483*	0.000	-0.535*	0.000	-0.416*	0.000

D=*

It is clear from Table No. 7 that there is a statistically significant correlation between weight and the circumference of the chest, abdomen, upper arm, thigh, forearm, and shoulders, and the thickness of the skin folds in the area of the chest, plate, stomach, and behind the upper arm, and deviations in the shoulder area (deformity of rounding of the shoulders, deformity of one shoulder falling, deformity of the two plate bones skewing) when The level of significance was 0.05, and there was no statistically significant correlation between age, height, and deviations in the shoulder area (deformity of rounding of the shoulders; deformity of one shoulder falling; deformity of the two bones of the plate drifting) at a level of significance of 0.05.

Discussion of Search Results:

In light of the statistical results of the research within the framework of the objectives and hypotheses, the limits of the research sample members, and the tests and measurements used, the research results can be discussed as follows:

The researcher attributes this disparity between players to the differences in the environments between them and the type of food they eat, in addition to the various genetic factors and the fluctuation that characterizes this stage, as they usually do not walk in a straight line, as these standards can differ at any moment in this stage.

This is consistent with Amin Al-Khouly and Jamal Al-Din Al-Shafi'i's (2001 AD) statement that this stage of life is characterized by the emergence of individual differences in the speed of growth (6: 217).

This is consistent with what was stated by **Amin Al-Khouly and Jamal Al-Din Al-Shafi'i (2001 AD)**, who noted that the emergence of individual differences in the speed of growth characterizes this stage of life. (6: 217). **Osama Kamel Rateb and Ibrahim Abd Rabbuh Khalifa (1999 AD)** stated that one of the most important physical characteristics of this age stage is a surge in height and weight growth for both sexes, accompanied by a widening of the shoulders and circumference of the buttocks, as well as an increase in length torso and the length of the legs. (3: 117)

The researcher also believes morphological measurements are critical for identifying a stage's characteristics and their relationship to texture. They can help determine the extent of their effect on a player's body and guide them to a game that suits their nature. Comparing the results with each other, the decrease in weight compared to height can reveal the effects of this decrease. **Ahmed Nasr El-Din Sayed (2003 AD)** emphasized the importance of these measurements in describing the human body and monitoring physical growth, especially in children at different age stages. He also highlighted the correlation between specific measurements and physical fitness elements (2: 254).

To answer the second question, which states, "What are spinal deviations and their prevalence in this age group?"

Table No. (4) shows standard spinal deviations in the research sample, including head thrust forward, lateral tilt, rounded shoulders, falling shoulders, scapula skewing, flat back, back convexity, lumbar concavity, and lateral bending. The range is (0.017) to (0.467), with a standard deviation between (0.131) and (0.499). In addition, **Table No. (5)** shows the percentages of spinal deviations, with the most common being 22.5% protrusion of plate bones, 17.5% shoulder fall, and 2.5% side bend.

Thus, the research reveals a high prevalence of spinal deviations among the younger generation, highlighting their dangers and inability to maintain a generation free of deviations. The study shows that the shoulder region is the most affected, with a high rate of spinal deviations. This aligns with **Muhammad Al-Shahat's 2004 AD** theory that postural deviations in the upper body, particularly in the spine and shoulder girdle, are due to daily posture habits such as swinging the shoulders and using them in front of the body, resulting in the body lowering its head. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the reasons behind these deviations and their treatment (19:30).

The researcher attributes the spread of these deviations to incorrectly sitting on inappropriate school chairs and desks for long periods, as they have standardized specifications that do not take into account individual differences between players in terms of the player's physical or age characteristics (morphological measurements). In addition, parents are unable to follow the appropriate special nutritional program. The player and what his essential dietary needs are.

These results are consistent with what was pointed out by **Hisham Jumaa Al-Karsawi (2004AD)(21)**, **Asmaa Taher Nofal (2005AD)(4)**, **Ihab Muhammad Imad Al-Din (2011AD)(7)**, and **Ahmed Muhammad Amara (2012AD)(1)** that deviations Posture is widespread at different levels of education as a result of reading, writing, and using computers for long periods, or the lack of school health requirements, or physical differences between players without taking this into account in school seats, or incorrect postural behaviour of young people, such as carrying a bag incorrectly or adopting positions such as walking, standing, and sitting incorrectly.

The third question is, "What is the relationship between some morphological measurements and spinal deflections in young gymnasts?"

Table No. (6) reveals a significant correlation between age, height, chest, abdomen, upper arm, thigh circumference, and skin fold thickness in the head area. The head forward thrust and lateral tilt deviations are correlated with age, height, chest, abdomen, upper arm, and thigh circumference. The head rushing forward deformity is significant at a significance level of 0.05, while weight, shoulder circumference, and forearm circumference do not. Deformity in the chest, plate, abdomen, behind the humers, and lateral tilt is significant at a significance level of 0.05.

The researcher suggests that deviations in a player's figure increase as they grow taller, have thinner body circumferences, and have thicker skin folds. These deviations can be attributed to poor posture, height, chest circumference, and weakness. Players' neck muscles are long and weak, while their anterior muscles are long and robust. Maintaining the same height for other school desks also increases deviations. Early height may cause tilting due to undeveloped bones, and distortion is expected due to relative softness measured by fully developed bones.

Table No. 7 reveals a significant correlation between weight, chest circumference, upper arm circumference, thigh, forearm circumference, and skin fold thickness in the shoulder area. The study also found a correlation between chest, plate, abdomen, back of the humors, and shoulder area deviations (roundness of shoulders, fall of one shoulder, and skewness of two plate bones) at a significant level of 0.05. However, there was no significant correlation between age, height, and shoulder area deviations (rotation of shoulders, fall of one shoulder, and skewers deformation of two plate bones) at a significance level of 0.05.

The researcher attributes this relationship to the fact that there is a correlation between weight, abdominal circumference, and lumbar concavity deformity, with a significance level of 0.05. However, there was no significant correlation between age, height, shoulder girdle muscles, upper body circumferences, or skin fold thickness in other areas. The study suggests these deviations are primarily due to decreased body weight, increased height, shoulder girdle weakness, and shoulder carrying. Finally, through the results, the researcher found that a player with decreased weight often has poor body flexibility and poor body flexibility, as evidenced by abdominal fold thickness, chest flabbiness, and deviations in the upper head. Weight gain with increased flabbiness contributes to increased concentration and limb deviations in lower parts, such as sucking of thighs, knocking of knees, and splaying of feet.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions:

In light of the research objectives and results, within the limits of the research sample and its characteristics, and based on the statistical treatments, the program, and the available capabilities of the tools used, and after presenting and interpreting the results, the researcher was able to reach the following conclusions:

- The arithmetic average of the morphological measurements under study reached the smallest value of the thickness (139 cm) and the most significant value (181 cm), with an arithmetic average of (159.245 cm)

and an apparent discrepancy in the weight variable, where the lowest value was (29 kg). The most significant value was (101 kg), with an arithmetic average of (52.152 kg), and the standard deviation ratios were (8.771) and (13.726), respectively.

- There is a statistically significant relationship between some morphological measurements and some spinal deformities in the research sample of young gymnasts.
- Morphological measurements reveal physical conditions like height increase, skin fold thickness increase, and weight loss/gain in children due to incorrect walking/sitting habits or weight carrying during training, particularly on the shoulder or back.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following based on the research objectives, questions, sample description, statistical treatments, results, and discussion:

- Early detection of posture and spinal deformities is crucial for gymnastics at all ages.
- They pay attention to the child's physical characteristics, monitor their weight through periodic morphology measurements, and provide appropriate food for young people.
- We promote posture awareness among trainers, educate young people on proper posture habits, and organize seminars and conferences to impart knowledge on posture deformities, detection techniques, and treatment methods.
- Through media programs, educate people about posture, its significance, how to treat its deformities, and how to prevent these deformities.
- The researcher suggests maintaining an individual's figure, achieving ideal body measurements by developing muscle strength in the abdomen, back, and shoulder area, and providing preventive programs to treat posture deviations early.

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